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**YUXARI SİNİF ŞAĞIRDLƏRİNDƏ FƏAL HƏYAT MÖVQEYİNİN
FORMALAŞDIRILMASI ÜZRƏ İŞƏ PEDAQOJİ RƏHBƏRLİK**

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**PEDAGOGICAL GUIDE TO FORMING AN ACTIVE LIFESTYLE AMONG HIGH
SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ РУКОВОДСТВО ПО ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ АКТИВНОГО
ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ У СТАРШЕКЛАСНИКОВ**

Xülasə. Yuxarı sinif şagirdlərində fəal həyat mövqeyinin formalaşdırılmasına pedaqoji rəhbərlik təlim və tərbiyə prosesinin ümumi qanunauyğunluqlarına əsasən həyata keçirilir. Müəllim şagirdlərin ətraf aləmlə fəal təmasında, həyatda fəal iştirakında, müstəqilliyində, öz yerini düzgün müəyyənləşdirilməsində, möhkəm əqidəyə malik olmasında bir subyekt kimi çıxış edir. Şagirdlərin dünyagörüşünün formalaşması məktəbdən başlayır.

Açar sözlər: *muəllim, şagird, məktəb, pedaqoji rəhbərlik, fəal həyat mövqeyi, formalaşdırma*

Summary. Pedagogical guidance on the formation of an active lifestyle in high school students is based on the general regularities of the educational and upbringing process. A teacher acts as a subject of the active engagement of students with the world, their active participation in life, independence, proper positioning and firm beliefs. The formation of students' outlook begins at school.

Key words: *teacher, student, school, pedagogical guidance, active lifestyle, formation*

Резюме. Педагогическое руководство по формированию активного образа жизни у старшеклассников основано на общих закономерностях учебно-воспитательного процесса. Учитель выступает субъектом активного взаимодействия учащихся с миром, активного участия в жизни, независимости, правильного позиционирования и твердых убеждений. Формирование мировоззрения учащихся начинается в школе.

Ключевые слова: *педагог, ученик, школа, педагогическое лидерство, активная жизненная позиция, формирование*

Schools contribute to the comprehensive and harmonious development of human beings. They must instill good qualities and habits in the education of students by upbringing them as personalities, train them to act conscientiously by considering the best of their abilities, to use social resources effectively, and to uphold moral

standards. Teachers play a major role in nurturing a growing generation, and they can rightly be regarded as the spiritual leaders of young people. In pedagogical guidance, it is crucial to ensure that students are not overloaded, that the activities are properly organized and implemented, and that the students who are left

behind are receiving the necessary pedagogical support. Teachers' job is not only to provide knowledge, but also to enhance students' social activity, because the social activity of a person is his / her civil perfection. An active lifestyle is an essential part of the formation and socialization of a person.

A teacher underlies the development of a young personality as a citizen and the formation of moral qualities. Teachers should ingrain a feeling of love for the motherland, respect for the parents and the elderly, and a responsible attitude in students, and promote a student's self-esteem. Students under the guidance of a teacher at school acquire the skills necessary for an active lifestyle in the various types of classroom and out-of-school educational work.

The formation of an active lifestyle occurs in the course of time. This process should start from pre-school.

Teachers' system of educational activities can consist of the following actions:

- 1) The organization of a unit sincere collective of students;
- 2) A comprehensive and individual study of students;
- 3) Struggling for the acquiring of deep knowledge and conscious discipline among students;
- 4) Preparation and carrying out extracurricular and out-of-school activities;
- 5) Providing public organizations with regular pedagogical training and advice;
- 6) Communication and cooperation with parents.

All these educational systems are closely bound with one another. Teachers should address some of these issues during the class, which they teach, and some during extracurricular activities.

Leading teachers of the Azerbaijani Republic efficiently benefit from pedagogical opportunities in out-of-classroom activities, and develop students' personal activeness taking into account their interests, abilities, age, and personal characteristics.

Extracurricular activities with high school students differ. These comprise of extracurricular reading activities, reading conferences, disputes and themed parties, excursions to exhibitions and museums, and tours around the country to get to

know it better. In addition, the organization of large-scale movie and theater screenings and the subsequent discussion of those movies and theatrical performances, overseeing the regular release of classroom wallpapers, arranging meetings with leading figures, intellectuals, writers, national heroes, labor veterans, involvement and participation in socially useful work, etc. include in effective classroom extracurricular activities.

One of the most important forms of extracurricular activities is teachers' supervision of doing homework. Supervision activates students and creates a sense of responsibility in them. Teachers should also assist in the selection of literature by examining the interest of a student during the process of supervision. For this reason, a teacher should work closely with public organizations and parents, and familiarize with students' home environment and home library. One of the main directions of extracurricular activities is the students' selection of specialty.

High school students' participation in national composition and essay competitions, Olympiads, and intellectual competitions is also of great significance for nurturing an active lifestyle. In some schools, such activities are forgotten about during pedagogical guidance and are considered only as the job of head teachers and public organizations. In accordance with the results of pedagogical experiments, we can say that teachers bear a huge responsibility in the formation of an active lifestyle in high school students. The effectiveness of the formation process highly depends on teachers' performance.

Mikhail Ivanovich Kalinin said at the time that it was much harder to discipline people than to teach and educate them, because the educator not only gives knowledge to the educated ones, but also influences the ordinary phenomena. M.I. Kalinin claimed that upbringing is one of the most difficult pedagogical activities, because the personal actions, in other words, the personal example of a teacher, play a key role.

Awareness, adequate knowledge and skills are very important in getting an active life too. Knowledge is acquired through the participation and guidance of a teacher. How, where, and in what kind of activities, can

knowledge and skills be used? In this sense, students need teacher support and advice.

The social and political activity of high school students requires initiative and independence. They are not always able to achieve this. Therefore, teachers should play the role of methodologist, consultant and helper for students in this issue. The way in which social-political activity is shaped is that a student can participate as a preacher, an advocate, a lecturer, an organizer in a socially useful work, a leader of the association, and a direct presenter in the activity. In this case, the pedagogical guidance of the teacher-advisor becomes more of an issue. One of the most difficult and main issues in pedagogical guidance is the determination of the educational impact and usefulness of social and political activities. In other words, only a teacher who has the right guidance can develop and improve students' ability to summarize and evaluate the results of their own activities.

It is important for teachers and educators, who are actively engaged in the formation of an active lifestyle in students, to know the psychological basis of an active life position. The formation of a person's spiritual world is a complex and constant process, and it is influenced by a number of factors. Self-awareness, proper self-evaluation, and self-enhancement to improve one's morale hold a significant place among these factors. If a teacher also participates directly with students in the implementation of socially useful activities, the event becomes more organized. Pedagogical staff should explain to students that socially useful work develops and broadens a person's outlook, knowledge, and enables them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

High school students learn to serve the community while engaging in socially useful work and eventually begin to understand their civic duties.

In addition to socially useful activities in general education schools, various lectures and clubs have been established, which should also provide pedagogical guidance.

Children's social organizations should be regularly assisted. Students' self-control must be strengthened. It is necessary to create conditions for students to be responsible for the organization of cultural events and let them be

the leaders of their own actions, that is, the events which they organized.

The diversity of forms and methods of cultural and collective work of high school students originates from the diversity of content. They should present these events in a timely and exemplary manner. Organizing group tours for parties, excursions, and movie and theater performances, and creating amateur artistic associations and drama clubs include in cultural-collective events. Pedagogical staff should help students in organizing such events. They advise pupils in the selection of artistic and dramatic works, the pedagogical and political correctness of the program of the amateur artistic association, the discussion of movies, theatrical performances, and artistic works in order to get one joint thought and achieve the best result in the organized events.

A teacher is the person closest to a student after his / her parents. Therefore, the active position of students in school and in life depends on the image, behavior and work of a teacher. A teacher should make sure that his / her activities are lively, interesting and highly scientific. Taking into account students' individual characteristics, teachers must be able to deal with them individually, be sensitive and attentive to them, and take care of them. Teachers must be fair in every case, sincere and kind towards every student. If every teacher fulfills these conditions and has the right pedagogical guidance, then students can adequately carry out their tasks. It can be concluded that the school, where the pedagogical staff contributes to the activities of children's social organizations, can improve the discipline, training and education of teenagers and thus create an active lifestyle for them.

Problemin aktualığı. Tədqiqat işində uşaq ictimai birliklərinin fəaliyyətinin mahiyyəti açıqlanır, uşaq ictimai birliklərinin funksiya və vəzifələri nəzərdən keçirilir, fəaliyyət sahələri, uşaq ictimai birliklərinin növləri göstərilir.

Problemin yeniliyi. Yuxarı sinif şagirdlərinin ictimai-siyasi fəallığı təşəbbüskarlıq və müstəqillik tələb edir. Onlar heç də həmişə buna tam nail ola bilmirlər. Odur ki, müəllim bu sahədə şagirdlər üçün metodist, məsləhətçi və köməkçi rolunu oynamalıdır. İctimai siyasi fəallığın necə formalaşması özünü onda göstərir ki, şagird təbliğatçı, təşviqatçı, müha-

zirəçi, ictimai-faydalı işdə təşkilatçı, dərək rəhbəri və fəaliyyətdə bilavasitə aparıcı kimi iştirak etsin.

Problemin praktik əhəmiyyəti. Uşaq ictimai birliklərinin fəaliyyəti böyüklər və uşaqların birgə fəaliyyətinin məqsədyönlü prosesidir, bunun vasitə-

silə gənclər öz ehtiyaclarını, pedaqoji qarşılıqlı fəaliyyətin təkmilləşdirilməsi baxımından cəmiyyətə prioritetlərini çatdırmaq, könüllülük əsasında fəaliyyət göstərmək imkanlarına malik olurlar.

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